

BOYSUN IN ANCIENT TIMES

Mahmudov Mirsaid

Nurmamatov Shahriyar

Termez State Pedagogical Institute .

Faculty of history,

direction of history

student of the second stage.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7808411>

There is a human being who is the progenitor, lineage, born and raised by himself he village, the city, so to speak, the Homeland wants to know its history". National the root of our being, of our culture, the STEM is paler.

I.A.Karimov

Abstract: This article is about the ancient period of Boysun, when it was written about who studied such caves as Teshtosh, Amir Temur, Machay, what finds were found. In addition, it was written by UNESCO that Boysun was recognized as an oral and intangible cultural masterpiece of mankind.

Keywords: Hole cave, Amir Temur cave, Machay cave, Neanderthal, Gerasimov.

As an oral and intangible cultural masterpiece of humanity of the cultural regional heritage of the Boysun district, 2001 was included in the list of "masterpieces of intangible heritage and oral creativity of mankind" by UNESCO on the basis of the project "Conservation of traditional culture of the Boysun district and folk art for 10 years General Program – National Registration and preparation". "Boysun has a high culture in the world as a center of ancient civilization, settling on an ancient trade route connecting Asia and India, reflecting its material and spiritual heritage, ancient and vibrant culture and nature, the dialogues of Zoroastrianism, Buddhism and Islam," noted UNESCO secretary general Koichiro Matsuura. Boysun district, which is included in the list of 47 masterpieces of culture that have a special place in the history of world civilization, is one of the urgent issues to go through the events of special attention in historiography, study its history and present it to the younger generation now.

The first phase (2003-2004) of the UNESCO Target Program for the preservation of Boysun folkloric and traditional culture was carried out with the help of financial support from the Japanese trust fund of the Japanese government. The next phase (2005-2014) was carried out on the basis of the 10th Annual "Master plan" program, aiming to give Boysun the status of elatlik-folkloric, archaeological and scenic (landscaped) Reserve. The first festival of open folkloric "Boysun spring", organized in Boysun with the support of UNESCO and the Uzbek government, was held on may 23-27, 2002. I. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the participants and guests of the Festival.A.Karimov addressed with his official congratulations. The festival featured 11 folkloric teams from Uzbekistan and "Gadjina" ensemble from Tajikistan, 24 Uzbek Bakhshis, 2 Kyrgyz manasists, 16 musicians from Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Japan. More than 40 scientists from Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Japan, the Republic of Korea, Russia and France attended the scientific conference at the festival` round, and the Boysun declaration was adopted at the scientific conference. The second festival was held on may 13-18, 2003 and was attended by 12 folkloric ensembles, costumes, designers from Uzbekistan and Tajikistan. Within the framework of the Festival, the

International Bakhshi poets ' review competition was held in Termiz, a scientific conference dedicated to the problems of maintaining a unique elatlik folkloric environment. The history of Boysun is an integral history of human history, historical sources have substantiated in scientific sources that the first stage of the cultural historical period in the development of mankind began in the Paleolithic (Greek "palayos" means ancient, "letos" means stone), that is, in the ancient stone age, since the weapons of Labor were made of stone. The fact that in Central Asia, the weapons of Labor characteristic of the Paleolithic era were found in the Boysun area, and it was improved and modified by our early ancestors, and technically gradually perfected, has found evidence in historical sources. Boysun as the first settlement of mankind was considered to be the stages of the Paleolithic in the middle and recent periods, as a space that played an important role in the emergence and mental improvement of man, comparative analysis was carried out in the sources. The oldest people on the territory of Uzbekistan have been living for more than 1 million of years, that is, since the early Paleolithic, the archaeological scientist, academician O'. Islamov wrote that " the study of monuments on the territory of Uzbekistan dating back to the early stages of the history of the emergence of man began in 1938. In the same year, a.P.Chief Okladnikov detachment for the study of the archaeology of the primitive period studied the Hole cave located in the Zovtalashgansoy gorge of Surkhandarya in the Boysun district. The Hole cave, dating from 100-40 Thousand Years BC, was originally built by the local historian G.V.It was identified by Parfenov in the 1930s. The cave, 1500 m above sea level, is 21 meters long, 20 meters wide and 9 meters high. The total area is 300 sq. m, of which 100 sq. site m has archaeological material that testifies to Neanderthal habitation. The monument consisted of 5 cultural layers, the cultural layer was 1.5 meters. This is a sign that the settlement has been abandoned several times. The remains of one campfire survive in each layer of the cave, and two in some. Many mountain goats, reindeer, hyacinths, bears, rabbits and bone remains of various birds have been found around these bonfires. Above all, the discovery of the grave of a Neanderthal' child aged 9-10 from the upper cultural layer has elevated the monument to a level of secular significance". This anthropological finding was of great interest, and from specialist scientists G.F. Debets, M.M. Gerasimov, M .D. Gremyaikius and V.A. The alekseevs showed enthusiasm in his study. It was discovered that the Neanderthal ' baby skull found was 1,450 centimetres cubic in size and scientifically substantiated that it belonged racially to the European and Old Asian group.

In world science, concepts, terms related to the discovery, scientific justification of the first people and their introduction into science appeared as a result of the emergence of primitive people, their anthropological structure, physical bodily changes in appearance, the expansion of their mental and thinking and the growth of their consciousness. One such term is Neanderthal people. The Neanderthal man found in the hole is a guru of ancient human "paleanthropes", close to much more modern humans with his cranial box, rib fragments, shoulder and thigh bones, and other postures. The term Neardental man entered Science in 1856 on the basis of the oldest human remains found near the town of Dussel'dor in the Neanderthal Valley of Germany. The neck of a Neanderthal man is 160 centimeters, the volume of his brain is 1440-1450 gr, but in relation to modern people there is a thick bulge above his eye, and a Neanderthal man lived in a pack of primitive people in Western Europe, typical of the must'e culture during the V'yurm glacier, usually living in caves, hunting large animals, making weapons,

The appearance of ancient settlements in the surkhandarya region is typical of the must'e stage of the Stone Age, and the boy's sklet, found in the hollow cave space on the Boysun mountain, was a universal discovery of its time, which allowed Central Asia to also be viewed as one of the regions in which humanity was formed. According to new data from the disciplines of Archaeology and anthropology, it was scientifically analyzed that the find existed seventy-five thousand years ago. Of the 667 bones found in the cave, 649 are deer bones. Since hunting required the participation of many people, it was one of the main factors that made primitive people Jeep to act together. In retrieval with a wounded Predator, people were often killed, sharing the prey they captured together. Women were engaged in picking, that is, picking fruits and berries, rooting, and prepared labor weapons. The famous anthropologist scientist and sculptor M. M. Gerasimov created the image of a child, the child's skull is very tight, the forehead is springy, low, the eyebrow is hanging. The chewing muscles are strong, the chin is flat, the position of the skull and the figure of The Hunchback is a sign that a person of that time is not yet used to adjusting his stature. He is very similar in appearance to the Neanderthal` - shaped people who lived in Europe. The taka horns placed around his grave supposedly protected the child from demons, a symbol of the Sun, confirming its religious significance. In the same place academic B.Gafurov's views seem to be much more notable, with the scientist considering the stone artifacts recovered from the hole to be of Middle Paleolithic age. Of the 2,859 stone objects found and studied in the cave, 2,520 pieces were broken, 134 pieces were made up of plate fragments, 94 pieces of stone weapons, 101 pieces of various shapes of cores, 10 pieces of stone fragments. In particular, 339 pieces of these stone items fall into the ranks of completed weapons. They may have been used by sharp-tipped stones as a monand to the blade, and for picking hunted animals, processing trees. These Neanderthal ' people hunted mainly mountain takas, deer, bears, hyenas and other small animals, which date back to the must'e period. In addition, the release of branches of mountain takas around the skeleton of the child brings to mind the fact that there was, apparently, a special funeral. With the discovery of ancient human qunalghas in many mountain caves, the important thing is that the child found in The Hollow caves of Boysuntog on the banks of the Turkon (Sherabad)River monand to the skull of the other bones are still missing as found in Central Asia with an entire head.

According to the opinion and conclusion of ancient scientists, the life in the cave of peritoneum continued even during the Mesolithic period. The cultural layer is about 40 meters thick, from which Mountain Goats, bears, turtle bones and various stone weapons made of Silicon, Flint, limestone, sandstone, yashma, quartzite and other volcanic rock rocks were found. Stone weapons included sequins, scrapers, stone knives, and stone chopsticks. Thanks to these findings, it is possible to determine the ancient life of the inhabitants of this area and the standard of living in the economic sphere. In total, 15 Upper Paleolithic settlements inhabited by ancient people were found in the Surkhan Oasis. The toshtosh monument is a monument dating back to the Middle Paleolithic (must'e) period found in the Southern Region of Uzbekistan.

Weapons such as sharp-tipped sequins, stone knives, Kirgiz, chopsticks were also found in the cultural layers. These stone weapons were used by the inhabitants who lived in the cave as scrapers, knives in cleaning the skin of the animal captured and nimiting its flesh. Many mountain goats, reindeer, hyenas, bears, rabbits and bone remains of various birds have been found around these bonfires. There are a lot of ancient Stone Age monuments located in the

Boysun area, another of such monuments is the Amir Temur cave. The cave is located much closer to the hollow cave, and is mainly of middle stone i.e. Mesolithic age. The primitive people who lived in the cave of Amir Temur were engaged in hunting and thermography. The stone weapons found in Amir Temur cave are much more similar to the stone weapons found in the Hole cave. Primitive people who lived in the cave of Amir Temur were engaged in hunting and thermoaging. The discovery of a large number of animal bones from here as a result of archaeological excavations in the cave is evidence of the above points. By the Middle Stone Age, as a result of the warming of the climate, primitive people began to build space, moving not only into caves, but also into lowlands and valleys. During this period, they followed in the footsteps of hunting prey in the hope of food, pursuing them and leading a mostly impulsive life. From the layers of the Amir Temur cave, a remnant of a campfire, wood, coal was found, which came 11.5 meters wide. The site was probably a temporary landing of Neanderthal' hunters due to its low and poisonous nature.

The discovery of a large number of animal bones from here as a result of the archaeological excavation work carried out in the cave is evidence of the above points. The existence of three cultural layers in the cave has been studied, with the first to second layers being dated to the last stone age, the lowest i.e. the third layer dating to the Middle Stone (MUST'e) age. By the Mesolithic period, a person became more and more adapted to the external environment, his living Oreol expanded. People began to see during this period not only eat in caves, but also settle on the plains. There were also dramatic changes in social relations. The men of the time became known in fan as the "HOMO SAPIENS" idirokli man. Modern humans, whose three races are europeoid, negiroid (Habash), and mangaloid disguises, also came into being around that time.

The last stage of the Stone Age, 40-35 thousand years ago BC, began in the Upper Paleolithic. It lasted from 12-10 Thousand Years BC. During this period, the people of the present day (cromanen) were formed. Human gangs began to live blood-to-blood. Fertility was strengthened by the mother and matriarchy emerged. In the distribution of cocktails, men were engaged in hunting, and women were engaged in household activities. From the layers of the Amir Temur cave, a remnant of a campfire, wood, coal, 1-1.5 meters wide, was found. The site may have been a temporary burial place for Neanderthal' hunters due to its low elevation and Zah. The Highland old people are told that this cave was named after Amir Temur, because Amir Temur came and lived with his navkars between 1360-1365 and performed military exercises and said that taiorgism was performed.

In 1951, the historian S.K.Kabanov conducted observation work in the cave "Amir Temir", located on the Boysuntog Ridge. But the cave does not carry out archaeological excavations, nor did the periodization go unnoticed. Only fragments of pottery from the 1x-10th centuries were found from the inner part of the cave. Based on them S.K.Kabanov theorized that the cave was the encampment of the mutineers led by Muqanna, who had karshi taken to the Arabs.

Machay cave is located between the villages of Upper Machay and lower Machay. Located just above the Machai shadow (Turkondarya) in the foothills of Boysuntog, Machai cave is a Mesolithic, that is, a large monument of the Middle Stone Age. A team of hunters and fishermen lived in Machay cave, this monument was erected in 1938-1941 by G.V. Opened and studied by Parfyonov. In 1937, archaeologist A.P.Okladnikov conducted scientific research by opening two layers dating back to the must'e period. The Archaeologist O'. Islamov studied

Machay cave in 1970-1971, proving that the stone and bone tools recovered from it are Mesolithic. Dating from the 7th to 6th millennia BC, archaeological excavations have found and studied stone hunting weapons, stone knives in many different forms, as well as bone bigiz, needles and a large amount of animal bones as well as human bones. Anthropologist scientist T. According to khojaev, the people who lived in the Machai cave are anthropologically of the europoid race.

The primitive people who lived in the Machai cave were mainly engaged in hunting and thermological activities of the assimilating farm. The process of domestication of wild animals during the same period also takes place precisely during the must'e period, and the remains of bone recovered from Machay cave also fully prove this point. interestingly, this monument is an invaluable resource in the study of the anthropological image of mankind and the animal world on the basis of the bone relic of people of that time. a large number of mountain goat, large and small horned animal bones were found and studied from the cave, resulting in the discovery of the mil. in the 1st century BC. The people who lived in the Machai cave in the VIII-VII millennia indicate that they switched to domestication of animals. And those people, that is, you and our ancient ancestors, began to develop skills in the economy of production, and not only to master the ready-made things that exist in nature. Machay cave is located on a natural Hill 70 meters above the river level. The entrance is facing South. This cave is about 20 meters wide, 11 meters deep, 3-2.5 meters high. Archaeological excavations have found and studied a large number of stone hunting weapons, stone knives, as well as bone-based bigiz igina and a large number of animal bones as well as human bones. The primitive people who lived in the Machai cave were mostly mistreated by the hunting and thermological practices of the assimilating farm. In addition, the process of domestication of wild animals during this period takes place precisely in the must'e period, and the remains of animal bones found in the Machay cave also fully prove. This process has been shown to have occurred in Machay cave between the 7th and 6th millennia. The most important thing is that Stone weapons made from this cave with a slave of our primitive ancestors and used according to their own needs were brought into the world of science. These stone weapons differ in their method and shapes made from stone weapons found in other Mesolithic mazilgos of Central Asia. The above stone weapons studied form a distinctive culture of the Mesolithic period, which gave rise to the name of the Machai culture in fanda. In surkhandarya region, one of the oldest Paleolithic-specific culture sources is the cave of Yetimkalos, this ancient source is located in the northwestern flank of the Yetimkalos mountain in the Boysun range of Boysun District, 25 mt south east of the district center, at an altitude of 880 metr. Formed in layers of gypsum from the Jurassic period. The mouth of the cave is 3.5 meters wide facing South, 1.7 meters high the internal structure is complex : a number of rooms and oriented in all directions. Consists of corridors of different sizes. Almost all of the corridors ended in narrowing at the end. They are 1-3 meters to 7-9 meters wide and 1-2 meters to 5 meters high. The stage features a cave wall and fallen rock fragments. The total length of the cave is 182 meters, the area of 2 is 360 m², the volume is more than 700 meters.

Studied in scientific research, scientifically analyzed by ancient scientists, Devkamar cave is a cave located at an altitude of 1315 meters on the southern flank of Mount Sarimos in Boysun raion, at a relative altitude of 160 meters above the foot of the mountain. The archaeological source is typical in the okhaktoshs of the Jurassic period ,the entrance is in the form of a ravoc, 20 meters wide, up to 13 meters high. The cave consists of several bays and Chambers, 5-10

meters wide. height 2-3 meters. The Sahni is nearly flat, covered by a layer of Guano. Traces of leaked mummies can be seen in the limestone crevices in the cave mouth section and in the cave-type ceiling. Inside, there are sidewalks up to 6 meters long, up to 1.5 meters wide and up to 0.7 meters high in each direction. The total length of the cave is 46 meters, the area is 423 m², the volume is 2682 m³. In conclusion, Boysunda is located in a convenient location according to historical, cultural, geographical and other aspects. As mentioned above, Boysun was instrumental in the foreign trade on the Great Silk Road. Because trade caravans connected the Lands of Bukhara, Khorezm, Samarkand, Kesh, Nakhshab, Soghd and Shosh with the Lands of Bactria-Toharistan and North India. As a result, the Great Silk Road laid the foundation for the rise of cultural development by connecting countries with each other with different socio-economic development.

References:

1. Aminjonova T.N. Story of ancient monuments. - T., "Teacher".
2. Annayev.T., Shaydullaev.Sh. tablets from the history of Surkhandarya. - T. 1997.
3. Azimov.M. Termiztarixi, Termiz, "Jayhun". 2001
4. Berdiyev.X., Ermatov.X. Tablets from the history of surkhandarya.- T., 1991.
5. History of independent Uzbekistan. New history of Uzbekistan. Book 3. East-T.: 2000.
6. Istoriya Novy gorodov Uzbekistana. - T: Fan. 1976 -.
7. Usmanov.Q. History of Uzbekistan. For academic lyceums and vocational colleges. - T., "The teacher", 2003.
8. Rajabov.B., Isomiddinov.S. In search of underground resources. - T.,: East. 2002.
9. Rakhmonov.He. Raskopki keramicheskix Pechey Sapalli na poselenii Bustan 4. IMKU. VIP. 15. T., 1979.
10. Tursunov.S.N., Kabulov.E.A., PardaevT, Murtazaev.B., and b. Surkhandarya is in the mirror of history. - T., 2001.
11. Tursunov S.N., Kabulov E.A., Pardaev.T, Murtozaev.B., History of surkhandarya. - Tashkent," Sharq", 2001
12. Kohna and New Town at the intersection of great roads. (team of authors) - T.: East, 2001.
13. Pugachenkova.G.A., Rtveladze E.V., Severnaya Bactria Taxaristan problem istorii I kulturi. - T. "Science", 1990.
14. S.Tursunov, Q, Rashidov" Boysun " Akademnashr publishing house, 2011;